

MANGO PEEL-DERIVED PECTIN FILMS FOR SUSTAINABLE ANTIBACTERIAL PACKAGING APPLICATIONS

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Abstract: *The increasing demand for sustainable packaging solutions has driven research toward biodegradable materials derived from agricultural waste. This study explores the valorization of mango peels, a prevalent fruit processing by-product, through a dual-extraction methodology to recover bioactive compounds and pectin. The optimized extraction protocols enabled the efficient isolation of pectin from the residual biomass, enhancing the economic and environmental value of the original feedstock. Biopolymer films were fabricated via solution casting using isolated pectin and bioactive extracts from mango peels, resulting in uniform, biodegradable materials suitable for scalable production. Structural and thermal characterizations using FTIR spectroscopy and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) confirmed the successful incorporation of functional bioactive compounds within the film matrix. Notably, the mango peel extracts and the resulting pectin films exhibited strong antibacterial activity against selected bacteria, as demonstrated by agar diffusion assays. When applied to fresh produce, the films effectively inhibited microbial growth and extended shelf life, demonstrating direct functional benefits beyond material sustainability. These results underscore a promising circular economy strategy, in which fruit processing waste is transformed into high-value packaging materials with built-in antimicrobial functionality. By leveraging the intrinsic bioactivity of mango peel-derived compounds, the developed films offer a biodegradable packaging solution that actively contributes to food preservation. This integrated approach addresses both environmental and food safety challenges, reinforcing the potential of agricultural waste valorization in advancing sustainable packaging technologies.*

Keywords: antibacterial activity, extraction, food waste valorization, mango peel, pectin, sustainable packaging

1 INTRODUCTION

The environmental impact of non-biodegradable plastic waste has intensified global efforts to seek sustainable alternatives, with global plastic consumption for packaging expected to nearly triple by 2060 (Stoica et al., 2024). Consequently, biopolymers have attracted significant attention as food packaging materials owing to their advantageous properties including non-toxicity, renewable sourcing, biocompatibility, and biodegradability (Dirpan et al., 2023). Agricultural waste offers promising feedstocks for developing biopolymer-based packaging materials (Khanashyam et al., 2023).

Mango (*Mangifera indica* L.), being one of the most cultivated tropical fruits worldwide, generates substantial quantities of processing waste, with peels constituting approximately 7-24% of the total fruit weight (García-Mahecha et al., 2023). These peels are rich in pectin, a naturally occurring polysaccharide with excellent film-forming properties, as well as bioactive compounds including

phenolic acids, flavonoids, and antioxidants that remain largely underutilized in conventional waste management practices (Chaiwarit et al., 2020; García-Mahecha et al., 2023).

Pectin-based films have gained great attention as sustainable packaging materials due to their biodegradability, biocompatibility, and barrier properties. However, the mechanical and functional limitations of pure pectin films often restrict their practical applications (Singaram et al., 2024). The incorporation of bioactive compounds derived from the same raw material source presents an innovative approach to enhance film functionality while maintaining the principles of circular economy and waste valorization. Additionally, the integration of plant-derived antimicrobial agents into biopolymer matrices addresses critical food safety concerns while extending product shelf-life through active packaging mechanisms.

The outcomes of this research contribute to the advancement of sustainable packaging technologies by demonstrating the feasibility of transforming agricultural waste into functional packaging materials with enhanced preservation properties, supporting both environmental sustainability and food security objectives.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Sample preparation

Bioactive extracts were obtained from mango peels using Soxhlet extraction. Dried mango peels (15 g) were placed in a cellulose thimble and extracted with 150 mL of ethanol under reflux for 5 h until the condensate became colorless. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator (Heidolph Laborota 4000 efficient, Schwabach, Germany). Mango ethanol extracts (MEE) were stored at -20°C until further use.

Pectin extraction from mango peels was performed using an acid-catalyzed process. The dried and crushed peels were extracted in acidified water (pH 1.5–2.0, citric acid) at 80–90 °C, then filtered. Pectin was precipitated from the filtrate by ethanol addition, washed with ethanol, and dried to constant weight.

For mango pectin film (MPF), dry pectin (2 g) was dissolved in deionized water at 80 °C. Glycerol (2 mL) was added, followed by dropwise addition of 0.2 M calcium chloride (CaCl₂) solution under continuous stirring until gel formation occurred. The gel was cast into petri dishes and dried at 50 °C for 24 h to obtain the final film. For MPF enriched with MEE (MPF_MEE), the procedure was identical with the addition of 10% w/w MEE during the dissolution step.

2.2 Characterization

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) spectra were recorded using a Spectrum 65 (Perkin Elmer, Waltham, MA, USA) in attenuated total reflection (ATR) mode, with 4 cm⁻¹ resolution over the range 4000–600 cm⁻¹, averaging 16 scans.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed using a TGA/DSC 3+ (Mettler Toledo, Greifensee, Switzerland). Samples were heated from 25 to 550 °C at a heating rate of 10 K/min under N₂ atmosphere (20 mL/min), followed by a 10-minute isothermal hold under O₂ atmosphere (20 mL/min).

Mechanical properties were evaluated using a universal testing machine (Shimadzu, AG-X plus 10 kN) according to ISO 527-1 standard. Tensile testing was performed with a gauge length of 50 mm, a preload of 0.03 N, and variable testing speeds (10 mm/min until 0.05% strain, then 100 mm/min until failure).

Optical microscopy was performed on MPF and MPF_MEE using a Keyence VHX-7000 digital microscope at 150x magnification.

The antibacterial activity of MPF_MEE films was evaluated qualitatively against Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*) and Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*) bacteria using the agar diffusion method. Briefly, agar plates were inoculated with prepared bacterial solution ($1-5 \times 10^6$ CFU/mL), MEE and MPF_MEE were placed directly on the inoculated agar plates and incubated for 24 h at 37 ± 1 °C.

Furthermore, fresh strawberries of uniform size and ripeness were selected for shelf-life evaluation. The first group of strawberries was wrapped in MPF, the second group was wrapped in MPF_MEE, and the third group was left unwrapped as a control. All samples were stored at ambient conditions (25 ± 3 °C, ambient humidity) and monitored for 14 days. Daily visual assessment evaluated surface appearance, decay progression, and overall preservation quality.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The FTIR spectrum (Figure 1) of MP shows characteristic polysaccharide absorption bands, including O–H stretching at 3400 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl groups and hydrogen bonds), C–H stretching at 2920 cm^{-1} (aliphatic bonds), C=O stretching at $1730-1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (carbonyl groups in esters and carboxylates), and C–O–C vibrations at $1200-1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (glycosidic bonds). The MPF spectrum shows preserved polysaccharide bands with enhanced intensity at 3400 cm^{-1} due to glycerol and water interactions. The band at 1600 cm^{-1} exhibits slight shifts attributed to Ca^{2+} -carboxylate crosslinking, confirming network formation. For MPF_MEE, minimal spectral changes occur in the $1700-1500$ and $1200-1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ regions, attributed to phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and other bioactive components containing carbonyl, aromatic C=C, and C–O functional groups. However, due to the low extract concentration (10% w/w), spectral changes are subtle, with higher concentrations expected to produce more distinct absorption band modifications (Demir et al., 2021).

Figure 1: Comparative FTIR spectra of MP, MPF, MPF_MEE

To further evaluate the thermal stability and degradation behaviour of synthesised MP-derived pectin films, TGA was conducted. TGA profile (Figure 2) demonstrated a multistage thermal decomposition. Initial mass loss occurred at 67 °C (2.1 % mass loss) corresponding to desorption of free or weakly bound water.

Figure 2: Thermal degradation profile of the MPF obtained by TGA

Primary decomposition of the polysaccharide chain initiated at 212-242 °C through dehydration and decarboxylation reactions. The main decomposition occurred at 323 °C with the highest mass loss (43.4%), attributed to complete polymer chain breakdown. Heating to 550 °C under nitrogen resulted in an additional 12.4% mass loss, while subsequent oxidative treatment yielded a total mass loss of 86.2%, leaving 13.8% inorganic residue. The results indicate thermal stability up to approximately 200 °C, beyond which rapid degradation occurs. The relatively high ash content (13.8%) suggests significant mineral content, likely from inherent pectin constituents or processing residues, which could potentially be reduced through enhanced purification procedures or modified film preparation methods.

Beyond thermal stability, the mechanical properties of the films are crucial for packaging applications. The stress-strain curve (Figure 3) demonstrates the typical behavior of a flexible, low-strength material characteristic of MPF. Low Young's modulus (0.38 ± 0.3 MPa) indicates high flexibility and easy deformation, while tensile strength (0.19 ± 0.03 MPa) reflects limited load-bearing capacity. However, the films exhibit exceptional elongation at break ($29.4 \pm 2.2\%$), exceeding values reported for comparable biopolymer films in the literature (Pereira et al., 2021; Syarifuddin et al., 2025). The combination of low stiffness and strength with high extensibility suggests potential applications requiring flexibility and deformability rather than structural rigidity. The mechanical behavior is influenced by film thickness (0.35 ± 0.05 mm), which contributes to the overall performance characteristics. These properties position the material favorably for packaging applications where conformability and stretch capacity are prioritized over mechanical strength.

Figure 3: Stress-strain curve of MPF

The mechanical behavior observed was further investigated through surface morphological analysis. Optical microscopy analysis (Figure 4) reveals differences in surface morphology between the film samples. The MPF film exhibits a relatively homogeneous surface with smooth topography, indicating uniform pectin matrix formation. In contrast, the MPF_MEE film displays increased surface roughness and heterogeneous microstructure. The incorporation of MEE (10% w/w) altered the pectin matrix organization, resulting in morphological changes that reflect the interaction between bioactive compounds and the polymer network.

Figure 4: Optical micrographs (150× magnification) of MPF (left) and MPF_MEE (right)

In addition to structural characterization, the functional properties of the films were assessed, particularly their antibacterial activity. The agar diffusion assay (Figure 5) demonstrates the antibacterial efficacy of MEE and MPF_MEE against selected bacteria. Clear inhibition zones are observed around both MEE and MPF_MEE samples when tested against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. The MPF_MEE films exhibit notable inhibition zones, indicating antibacterial activity attributed to the incorporated bioactive compounds from mango peel ethanol extract. The phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and other bioactive substances present in the extract contribute to the antibacterial properties through mechanisms such as cell membrane disruption and enzyme inhibition (Liu et al., 2025). The results demonstrate effectiveness against both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacterial strains, highlighting the broad-spectrum antibacterial potential of the bioactive compounds, which supports the application of bioactive extract-enriched films in food packaging, where microbial growth inhibition is crucial for food safety and extension of shelf-life.

Figure 5: Inhibition zones of MEE and MPF_MEE against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*

Furthermore, to validate the practical application potential, the films were evaluated for their effectiveness in food preservation. Figure 6 demonstrates the preservation efficacy of different pectin films on strawberry quality over 14 days at ambient temperature.

Figure 6: Visual assessment of strawberry preservation showing reference (unwrapped), MPF, and MPF_MEE treatments over 14 days of storage at ambient conditions (25 °C)

The unwrapped control strawberry exhibited rapid deterioration, showing visible decay after 4 days with extensive mold growth and complete degradation by day 14. Strawberries wrapped in MPF films displayed delayed spoilage compared to the control, though signs of decay including color changes, surface wrinkling, and mold development were evident after 14 days. The MPF_MEE films provided superior preservation performance, with wrapped strawberries maintaining better color retention, structural integrity, and significantly reduced mold growth throughout the storage period. The enhanced protective effect demonstrates that incorporation of bioactive compounds from MEE improves the antimicrobial and antioxidant properties of the pectin matrix, effectively extending fruit shelf-life. These results indicate the potential of bioactive extract-enriched pectin films as sustainable packaging materials for perishable produce preservation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Mango peel-derived pectin films were successfully prepared and characterized, demonstrating suitable properties for food packaging applications. The films demonstrated thermal stability up to 200 °C, high flexibility (29.4% elongation), and high antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Shelf-life evaluation showed superior preservation of strawberries wrapped in bioactive-enriched films compared to controls over 14 days. These results indicate that synthesized films represent a promising sustainable packaging solution for extending the shelf-life of perishable produce through combined barrier and antibacterial properties.

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